

Biochemical Comparison of Selected Salivary Parameters in Periodontal Health and Disease: A Cross-sectional Study

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Abstract

Aims & Objectives: To evaluate and compare the salivary calcium, phosphorous, alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and Potential of Hydrogen (pH) levels in periodontally healthy subjects and in patients with gingivitis and periodontitis.

Material and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted on participants who visited out patient department of periodontics, Mamata dental College, Khammam. Based on the Inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of 90 patients were included in this study and were divided into 3 groups of each group 30 patients, i.e. Group-1, Group-2 and Group-3 based on Pocket depth (PD), Clinical Attachment Level (CAL). Group 1 included healthy subjects with sulcus depth ≤ 3 mm with no CAL and Bleeding On Probing (BOP) whereas Group 2 included chronic generalized gingivitis subjects with sulcus depth ≤ 3 mm with no CAL but presence of BOP and Group 3 included chronic generalized periodontitis subjects with PD > 4 mm as well as CAL > 4 mm with or without BOP. The clinical parameters like Plaque Index (PI), Gingival Index (GI), Oral Hygiene Index –Simplified (OHI-S), PD and CAL were recorded.

Results: Statistical analysis was done using, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 25.0. Descriptive statistics was used for scaled data, and Kruskal Wallis test was performed for inter-group comparisons. Pair wise comparison was done using post-hoc analysis. The correlation between clinical and salivary parameters was done using Spearman correlation test. Confidence interval was set at 95% ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Within the limitations of the present study, Patients with chronic periodontitis showed the highest values whereas periodontally healthy subjects showed the least values of calcium, phosphorus, alkaline phosphatase and pH values among the three groups.

Keywords: salivary calcium, phosphorous, alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and Potential of Hydrogen (pH), Salivary Biomarker.

Introduction

Complex host-parasite interactions that result in alveolar bone resorption, periodontal ligament degradation, gingival inflammation, and loss of connective tissue attachment are the hallmarks of periodontal disease. Affecting 5%-30% of adults, it is the second most common oral illness after dental caries.^[1]

Pathogenic microbes are necessary for the development of periodontal disease, but they are insufficient for the destruction of periodontal tissues. Like many other chronic diseases, periodontal disease may develop as a result of various factors that impact the host's response to bacterial assault. Certain enzymes are secreted during the development of periodontal disease from the affected area's epithelial and connective tissue cells, polymorphonuclear leukocytes, dead or dying periodontium cells, and inflammatory cells.^[2]

An objectively measurable sign of a diseased process, a normal biologic process, or the pharmacological response to a therapeutic intervention is called a biomarker. Different substances, including as Ribonucleic Acid (RNA), Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA), antibodies, lipids, metabolites, and proteins, can function as biomarkers. Changes in their composition, capabilities, or behaviours may be linked to the beginning, development, or even reversal of a certain illness. It can be helpful to comprehend and assess the relevance of a distinct biomarker profile when determining the existence, distribution, or even probability of a disease.^[3]

The use of biomarkers in oral diagnostics has presented significant challenges for disease activity assessment, prognosis determination, and screening. Microorganisms and their byproducts, immunological and inflammatory products, enzymes originating from host cells released during connective tissue disintegration, and bone resorption are a few examples of potential periodontal biomarkers.^[1] When it comes to forecasting current or future disease activity, biomarkers can be an effective tool.

Saliva is an ideal medium to investigate for illness and health surveillance. Because saliva is a sign of health not only in the oral cavity but throughout the body, it is referred to as a "mirror of the body."^[4] Saliva is an ultrafiltrate of plasma and a complicated biological fluid.^[5] It's a useful bodily fluid with a variety of proteins, messenger Ribonucleic Acid (mRNA), and DNA that can

be applied in clinical settings and as biomarkers for translation. Proteomic, genomic, and microbiological biomarkers are the several categories of salivary biomarkers.^[4]

Saliva's buffering ability is a crucial component that supports both tooth remineralisation and the preservation of salivary Potential of Hydrogen (pH). *Porphyromonas gingivalis* has a higher level of proteolytic activity at alkaline pH values; growth requires a pH of 7.5. Plaque mineralisation is promoted by an alkaline pH, which is favourable for calcium phosphate deposition. The salivary flow rate and pH were higher in the groups that were more likely to develop periodontitis^[6].

Specific salivary enzyme activity measurements may be helpful in the identification of periodontal disease in humans. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) is an intracellular enzyme with a metabolism that is dependent on bone. It is released from polymorphonuclear cells, osteoblasts, and periodontal ligament osteoblasts. As inflammation and plaque buildup increase, so does the quantity of ALP^[2]. Elevated ALP activity may be a sign of more extensive cellular damage and severe periodontal disease due to active, destructive processes in the alveolar bone.^[3]

The purpose of the periodontal diagnostic process is to provide relevant data regarding the amount and severity of the current periodontal disease activity. In addition to providing crucial information during the disease monitoring stages of periodontal therapy, this diagnostic data aids in the formulation of the diagnosis and treatment plan^[1]. It is rather easy and affordable to measure the pH and ALP, phosphorus, and calcium concentrations in saliva.^[2] Thus, the purpose of this study was to assess and compare the levels of alkaline phosphatase, calcium, phosphorus, and pH in saliva from individuals with gingivitis and periodontitis to those who were periodontally healthy.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted on 90 participants from the outpatient Department of Periodontics, Mamata Dental College, Khammam, Telangana, during June 2022 to January 2023. The levels of salivary calcium, phosphorus, alkaline phosphatase, and pH in periodontally healthy individuals and patients with gingivitis and periodontitis were assessed and compared in a cross-sectional study. The study was approved by the institutional ethical review board of Mamata Educational Society (Ethical clearance No: MDC_KT_20201103003D). The study was done in conformity with the Helsinki Declaration, and all subjects provided written informed consent before commencing the study.

In this study, 90 patients in total, age ranging between 20-45 years were classified into three groups, Group-1(30patients), Group-2(30patients), and Group-3(30patients) according to Pocket Depth (PD) and Clinical attachment Level (CAL). In Group 1, participants were in good health and had a sulcus depth of less than 3 mm, no attachment loss, and Bleeding On Probing (BOP) [Fig 1]. In Group 2, participants had chronic gingivitis and a sulcus depth of less than 3 mm, no attachment loss, but BOP was present [Fig 2]. In Group 3, participants had chronic periodontitis and had periodontal pockets larger than 4 mm, along with clinical attachment loss greater than 4 mm, either with or without BOP [Fig 3]. Before the study began, informed consent was obtained from each participant after informing them regarding the purpose and study design. Inclusion criteria consisted of, Systemically healthy patients, Patients aged between 20-45 years, Patients who had not received any periodontal treatment in the past 6 months. Patients with known systemic diseases which can have an effect on periodontal conditions like diabetes, renal disease, hepatic disease, arthritis and malignant diseases were excluded. Those with history of antibiotic usage during the previous six months, Pregnant and lactating women, Patients with less than 15 teeth in the oral cavity were also excluded from our study. For clinical examination, Under bright lighting, patients underwent a thorough evaluation using a mouth mirror, an explorer, a University of North Carolina (UNC-15) periodontal probe. Clinical parameters were recorded, including Plaque Index (PI), Gingival Index (GI), Oral Hygiene Index-Simplified (OHI-S), PD, and CAL. Before the trial began, patients who satisfied the selection requirements were told about the protocol and their written informed consent was obtained.

For the collection of saliva samples,^[1] Two hours after the last meal, between 10 and 11 a.m., an unstimulated 5 ml whole saliva sample was taken in order to standardise the collection in accordance with the circadian cycle. Before a saliva sample was taken, the patients were instructed to properly rinse with distilled water. The patients were instructed to swallow any leftover saliva in their mouths five minutes following the oral rinse. While saliva was being collected, the subjects were instructed to stop talking, to droop their heads, and not to cough up mucus. The participants were then instructed to let as much saliva to pool on their tongue as possible, and then to expectorate into the collecting vessel until the required amount was gathered [Fig 4]. To prevent pH variations related to time, the saliva's pH was measured right away following collection using pH strips [Fig 5]. Collected saliva samples were kept at the temperature between 2-4°C. There, they were used for spectrophotometric estimation of salivary calcium, phosphorus, and alkaline phosphatase using a semi-auto analyser [Fig6]. Using Arsenazo reagent, the amount of inorganic salivary calcium was estimated. Salivary phosphorus was estimated using the ammonium molybdate method, and salivary alkaline phosphatase was estimated using a modified version of the International Federation of Clinical Chemistry (IFCC) method.

Results: Version 25.0 of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program (International Business Machines (IBM) Corporation, Armonk, New York.) was used for the statistical analysis. For scale data, descriptive statistics were employed, and for intergroup comparisons, the Kruskal Wallis test was performed. Post-hoc analysis was used to do pair wise comparisons. The Spearman correlation test was used to determine the relationship between clinical and salivary data. A 95% confidence interval was used. A significance level of Probability (p) <0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Discussion: Five to thirty percent of adult population suffer from periodontal disease, one of the most prevalent bacterial infections in humans^[7]. Complex host-parasite interactions, alterations in the composition of microbes, modifications to the immune system's inflammatory response, and an increase in oxidative stress are the hallmarks of periodontal disease. These factors cause gingival inflammation, loss of connective tissue attachment, destruction of the periodontal ligament, and resorption of alveolar bone^[8]. The World Health Organisation reports that 5–15% of people worldwide suffer from severe periodontitis, which results in tooth loss^[9]. Salivary secretions have been found to play a similar role in clinical dentistry as blood, which is widely used for both diagnosis and tracking the course of disease. Many researchers have been interested in using saliva for diagnostic purposes, mostly due to its non-invasive nature and relatively easy collecting process. Numerous proteins, antibodies, and other indicators found in saliva are crucial for diagnosis. Saliva is easier to gather, store, and transport than serum, which gives it significant advantages as a diagnostic tool^[3].

In a standard dental office, gingival crevicular fluid is difficult to obtain^[10]; instead, it needs to be collected by a qualified healthcare professional using the correct method^[11]. Saliva is widely accessible, simple to gather, appropriate for repeated examinations, a viable non-invasive diagnostic tool, and appropriate for mass screening initiatives^[12]. Furthermore, biomarkers originating from both the host and biofilm bacteria have been found in saliva^[13]. Salivary gland secretions, gingival crevicular fluid, leucocytes, microbes, and desquamated epithelial cells make up the composition of saliva. Compared to gingival crevicular fluid, entire saliva can be collected more readily, in large quantities, and with less discomfort. Since saliva is made up of secretions from the gingival crevicular fluid, it contains enzymes that are secreted during periodontal infections by host cells in the periodontal pocket^[7]. The best efficacy of salivary enzyme analysis for assessing the response to periodontal therapy was reported by Jabali et al. in 2019^[14]. There is evidence to suggest a possible correlation between periodontal disease and salivary biomarkers.

This study evaluated salivary levels of calcium, phosphorus, ALP, and pH in periodontal disease and correlated them with clinical periodontal parameters because the evaluation of salivary biomarkers is a non-invasive, reasonably simple, and cost-effective method to diagnose diseases. According to the current study's findings, the participants with periodontitis had considerably greater salivary calcium levels than the gingivitis and healthy groups. Patients with periodontitis may have had a higher capacity for remineralisation than people without periodontal disease, which may have contributed to the rise in salivary calcium levels in these patients. These results are in accordance with studies done by Vasavi et al. 2016^[15], Rane et al. 2017^[16], Vivek et al. 2018^[17]; Fiyaz, 2013^[18]; Sewon, 1990^[19]; Patel, 2016^[11]. The amounts of calcium in saliva may vary depending on dietary calcium intake and overall calcium turnover. Research indicates that one of the key factors contributing to the development of periodontal disorders is salivary calcium's affinity for being quickly absorbed by tooth plaque.

Salivary phosphorus levels in the three groups compared in this study showed that the group with periodontitis had significantly greater levels than the group II and group I. This could be the result of a rise in plaque scores between the groups, Fiyaz, 2013^[18], Ashley et al., 1991^[20], Rajesh, KS et al., 2015^[6]. Cohort studies are necessary to confirm the association between periodontal disorders and systemic bone density, as cross-sectional studies may not be able to do so. In contrast to gingivitis and healthy participants, the current investigation found that patients with chronic periodontitis had higher salivary ALP levels. These findings support a prior study's conclusion that salivary ALP can be utilised as a biomarker since it indicates periodontal tissue inflammation and damage, Dabra et al. 2012^[21], Adesakin et al. 2016^[22], Koirala et al. 2020^[23], Mushtaq et al. 2020^[24]. Patients with periodontitis may have elevated salivary ALP levels as a result of tissue changes brought on by host-parasite interaction. Certain enzymes are secreted during the development of periodontal disease from the affected area's epithelial and connective tissue cells, polymorphonuclear leukocytes, dead or dying periodontium cells, and inflammatory cells^[2].

The study discovered a moderate to strong, positive, and statistically significant association between the clinical parameters evaluated and the salivary biochemical markers. This suggests that salivary calcium, phosphorus, ALP, and pH levels rise in correlation with elevated plaque levels, gingival inflammation severity, poor oral hygiene, PD and CAL. This results are similar with study by Pradhan et al.2019^[25]. According to the current study's findings, people who have greater levels of salivary mineralisation factors, such as high salivary pH and inorganic salivary calcium and phosphorus, may be more susceptible to periodontitis. Elevations in salivary calcium subsequently correspond to elevated plaque calcium levels, making it easily remineralised [Ashley 1991^[20], Kinane 2000^[26]. Thus, indicators such as pH, ALP, phosphorus, and calcium in saliva can be taken into account when assessing the diagnosis and prognosis of periodontal tissues in both healthy and diseased states.

The limited sample size of the current study is one of its shortcomings. The present study was unable to show the impact of age-appropriate calcium modifications and diet, and the results would have been supported if a comparison of the assessed parameters had been possible following non-surgical periodontal care (scaling and root planing). The clinical criteria used in traditional periodontics are mostly inadequate for identifying the locations of active disease, tracking the effectiveness of treatment, and determining the degree of vulnerability to further disease progression. Saliva is a non-invasive, excellent source of therapeutically relevant information regarding oral health and disease because it contains particular biomarkers linked to the etiology of periodontal diseases. To make firm judgements and demonstrate the significance of saliva in identifying and gauging the degree of periodontal disease, further longitudinal studies spanning a large sample size with monitoring of dietary intake such as calcium would be needed.

Conclusion: Within the limitations of the present study, it can be concluded that there is a positive correlation between salivary calcium, phosphorus, ALP and pH levels and chronic periodontitis. It has been observed that as the periodontal disease severity increases the salivary calcium, phosphorous, ALP and pH levels were also increased. These parameters are potential biochemical markers for evaluating the diagnosis and prognosis of periodontal tissues in disease and health. However, further studies should be carried out to evaluate the relationship with periodontal therapy and on long term basis with large sample size to draw a definitive conclusion.

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Tables

Table1: Mean comparison of salivary calcium levels between groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Z value	P value
Group1	30	5.3523	0.86648	47.475	0.000*
Group2	30	6.9309	1.48993		
Group3	30	10.2709	0.92494		
Pairwise comparison-PostHoc analysis					
Comparison between		Mean difference		P value	
Group1	Group2	-1.578		0.001*	
	Group3	-4.918		0.000*	
Group2	Group3	-3.340		0.000*	

KruskalWallistest; $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant

Table2: Mean comparison of salivary phosphorous levels between groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Z value	P value
Group1	30	1.8023	0.80420	51.135	0.000*
Group2	30	3.6395	0.88847		
Group3	30	5.9514	1.05102		
Pairwise comparison-PostHoc analysis					
Comparison between		Mean difference		P value	
Group1	Group2	-1.837		0.001*	
	Group3	-4.149		0.000*	
Group2	Group3	-2.311		0.000*	

KruskalWallistest; $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant

Table3:MeancomparisonofsalivaryALPlevelsbetweengroups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Z value	P value
Group1	30	4.9209	2.86309	30.364	0.001*
Group2	30	11.1741	11.23828		
Group3	30	16.0655	8.79079		
Pairwisecomparison-PostHocanalysis					
Comparisonbetween		Mean difference		P value	
Group1	Group2	-6.253		0.020*	
	Group3	-11.144		0.000*	
Group2	Group3	-4.891		0.002*	

KruskalWallistest; $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant

Table4:MeancomparisonofsalivarypHlevelsbetweengroups

Group	N	Mean	SD	Z value	P value
Group1	30	6.4364	0.27868	57.509	0.000*
Group2	30	8.2227	0.32504		
Group3	30	9.2773	0.26535		
Pairwisecomparison-PostHocanalysis					
Comparisonbetween		Mean difference		P value	
Group1	Group2	-1.786		0.000*	
	Group3	-2.840		0.000*	
Group2	Group3	-1.054		0.000*	

KruskalWallistest; $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant

Table5:Correlationbetweensalivaryparametersandoralparameters

Salivaryparameters		PI	GI	OHI-S	PB	CAL
Salivarycalcium	rvalue	0.799	0.756	0.834	0.754	0.737
	P value	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*
Salivary phosphorous	rvalue	0.787	0.812	0.797	0.762	0.754
	P value	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*
Salivary ALP	rvalue	0.598	0.570	0.675	0.584	0.587
	P value	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*
Salivary pH	rvalue	0.874	0.874	0.861	0.827	0.799
	P value	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*

Spearman correlation test; $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant

FIGURE LEGENDS:

Fig1.Assessmentofprobingdepth&CALingroup1

Fig2.Assessmentofprobingdepth &CALingroup 2

Fig3. Assessmentofprobingdepth &CALingroup3

Fig4:Collectionofsaliva sample

Fig5:pHofsalivameasuredusingpHstrip

Fig6:SemiAutoanalyzersedforspectrophotometric analysis